

Generalised and Simplified Treatment of the Mixture-Method for the Application to Parachor, Rheochor, Lyoparachor etc.

V. R. Shastry, H. G. Asawa and W. V. Bhagawat

An equation has been evolved to calculate the parachor value in a single step and applicable to the most general and multicomponent systems.

Hamric and Andrew¹ were the pioneers in applying the law of additivity to evaluate the parachors of solutes from the binary systems of solutions. The series of equations for the application of mixture law can be written as:—

$$P_m = \frac{M_m \gamma m t}{D_m} \quad (1)$$

$$M_m = x M_s + (1-x) M_S \quad (2)$$

$$x = \frac{W_s/M_s}{W_s/M_s + W_S/M_S} \quad (3)$$

$$P_m = x p_s + (1-x) P_S \quad (4)$$

and therefore

$$P_s = \frac{P_m - (1-x) P_S}{x} \quad (5)$$

Where letters P, M, γ , D, W and X refer respectively to parachor molecular weight, surface tension, density, actual weight and molar fraction. The subscripts, m, s and S refer to mixture, solute and solvent, respectively. Thus P_s = parachor of solute while P_m and M_m refer to parachor and mean molecular weight of the mixture and so on.

It is evident from the above series of the equations that, at least four equations are involved in the calculations, for arriving at the final value of P_s . A careful survey of the literature shows that workers have calculated the parachor values of solutes by using the above procedures since all of them have tabulated the values of x, D_m , γm , M_m , P_m , and P_s .

But unfortunately the above procedure is laborious, tedious and time consuming. We have, however derived a more accurate method, involving only one equation, enabling to calculate the parachor value in a single step only, and applicable to the most general, multi component systems, constituted by n components.

Derivation of the equation:

If a system is constituted by n components such that:—Weights of the components are:—

$$W_1, W_2, W_3, \dots, W_r, \dots, W_n$$

Molecular weights are

$$M_1, M_2, M_3, \dots, M_r, \dots, M_n$$

Parachors are

$$P_1, P_2, P_3, \dots, P_r, \dots, P_n.$$

Molar fractions are

$$X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_r, \dots, X_n.$$

then the equations 2, 3 and 4 applicable to two component systems can be extended on the basis of additivity law, to n component systems in the form

$$M_m = X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2 + \dots + X_r M_r + \dots + X_n M_n \quad \dots (6)$$

$$X_r = \frac{W_r}{M_r} \bigg/ \frac{W_1}{M_1} + \frac{W_2}{M_2} + \dots + \frac{W_r}{M_r} + \dots + \frac{W_n}{M_n} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$P_m = X_1 P_1 + X_2 P_2 + \dots + X_r P_r + \dots + X_n P_n \quad \dots (8)$$

Now from (1)

$$P_m = \frac{M_m \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_m}$$

so that by substituting the values of P_m and M_m from (6) and (8) in (1) one gets

$$X_1 P_1 + X_2 P_2 + \dots + X_r P_r + \dots + X_n P_n = \frac{(X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2 + \dots + X_r M_r + \dots + X_n M_n) \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_m}$$

$$\text{Or } X_r P_r = \frac{(X_1 M_1 + X_2 M_2 + \dots + X_r M_r + X_n M_n) \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_m} -$$

$$-(X_1 P_1 + X_2 P_2 + \dots + X_{r-1} P_{r-1} + X_{r+1} P_{r+1} + \dots + X_n P_n)$$

$$P_r = \frac{1}{X_r} \left[(X_1 M_1 + X_r M_r + \dots + X_n M_n) \frac{\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_m} - (X_1 P_1 + \dots + X_{r-1} P_{r-1} + \dots + X_n P_n) \right]$$

$$\text{or } P_r = \frac{1}{\frac{W_r}{M_r}} \left[\frac{\frac{W_1 \cdot M_1}{M_1} + \dots + \frac{W_n \cdot M_n}{M_n}}{\frac{W_1}{M_1} + \dots + \frac{W_n}{M_n}} + \dots + \frac{\frac{W_n \cdot M_n}{M_n}}{\frac{W_1}{M_1} + \dots + \frac{W_n}{M_n}} \right] \frac{\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_m}$$

$$\left[\frac{W_1 P_1}{M_1} + \dots + \frac{W_{r-1} P_{r-1}}{M_{r-1}} + \dots + \frac{W_{r+1} P_{r+1}}{M_{r+1}} + \dots + \frac{W_n P_n}{M_n} \right] \frac{\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\frac{W_1}{M_1} + \dots + \frac{W_n}{M_n}}$$

$$\text{Or Pr} = \left(\sum_{a=1}^n \frac{W_a}{M_a} \right) \cdot \frac{Mr}{Wr} \left[\left\{ \frac{W_1 + W_2 + \dots + W_n}{Dm} \cdot \frac{\gamma m^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Dm} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{a=1}^n \frac{W_a}{M_a} \cdot Pa \cdot ca}{Ma} \right\} \right]$$

Where $ca=0$ when $a=r$ and $ca=1$ when $a \neq r$

$$\text{Or Pr} = \frac{Mr}{Wr} \left[\frac{Wm}{Dm} \cdot \frac{\gamma m^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Dm} - \sum_{a=1}^n \frac{W_a}{M_a} \cdot Pa \cdot ca \right] \quad (9)$$

Thus equation (9) shows that parachor value Pr of any r th component in a system of n components can be calculated in a single step only, provided all the quantities on R.H.S. are known.

It is easy to see that for binary and ternary systems, the equation (9) takes up the forms (10) and (11) respectively as given below:—

$$Ps = \frac{Ms}{Ws} \left[\frac{Wm}{Dm} \cdot \frac{\gamma m^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Dm} - \frac{Ws}{Ms} \cdot Ps \right] \quad (10)$$

$$P_1 = \frac{M1}{W1} \left[\frac{Wm}{Dm} \cdot \frac{\gamma m^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Dm} - \left\{ \frac{W_2}{M_2} P_2 + \frac{W_3}{M_3} P_3 \right\} \right] \quad (11)$$

Thus it is clear that the equations (9) to (11) derived above help to calculate the parachor value of a substance, directly in a single step by using data on weights only, there being no need of calculating x , Mm , Pm etc. in several steps and then arriving at the final value of Ps . Since, $\frac{P_a}{M_a}$, $\frac{P_b}{M_b}$ etc. are constants, the equation (10) and (11) can be written as

$$Ps = \frac{Ws}{Ms} \left[\frac{Wm}{Dm} \cdot \frac{\gamma m^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Dm} - K_1 W_s \right] \quad \dots (12)$$

$$P_1 = \frac{W_1}{M_1} \left[\frac{Wm}{Dm} \cdot \frac{\gamma m^{\frac{1}{2}}}{Dm} - \left\{ K_2 W_2 + K_3 W_3 \right\} \right] \quad \dots (13)$$

which further signifies the procedure for the solutions of various concentrations at various temperatures involving the same substances.

The equation derived by us for parachor can further be generalised for the analogous constants like rheochor (R), lyoporachor (L) etc.

For example, rheochor is given by

$$R = \frac{M\eta^{1/2}}{D-d} \text{ where } n = \text{coefficient of viscosity}$$

this equation is evidently analogous to the equation for parachor

$$\text{viz., } P = \frac{M\gamma^{1/2}}{D-d}$$

Further, Dr. Bhagwat and coworkers² have shown that the mixture law is applicable in the case of Rheochor also and the useful equations being $R_m = X R_s + (1-X) R_a$

$$P_m = \frac{M_m \gamma^{1/3}}{D_m}$$

which are again formally similar to the equations for parachor.

It is justified therefore that the equation (9) derived in the case of γ component systems for the parachor can be written for Rheochor as

$$R_r = \frac{M_r}{W_r} \left[\frac{W_m}{D_m} - \gamma_m^{1/3} - \sum_{a=1}^n \frac{W_a}{M_a} R_a \epsilon_a \right] \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{where } \epsilon_a = 0 \\ \text{when } a = r \\ \text{and } \epsilon_a = 1 \\ \text{when } a \neq r \end{array}$$

By adopting the similar mode of logic and procedure, it is reasonable to suggest that if Parachor Rheochor etc. analogous constants are represented by the generalised symbol 'Z' then

$$Z_r = \frac{M_r}{W_r} \left[\frac{W_m}{D_m} (X) P - \sum_{a=1}^n \frac{W_a}{M_a} Z_a \epsilon_a \right] \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{where } \epsilon \text{ has meaning} \\ \text{given above.} \end{array} \quad (14)$$

Where $E \theta$ has the meaning given in (9) and x refers to any property like surface tension (γ) (r) or viscosity (η) or latent heat of vaporisation (L) etc, and p is an appropriate power of x depending upon the property, for example

$p = \frac{1}{2}$ in the case of surface tension and $p = 1/3$ in the case of viscosity.

DISCUSSION

Equation (14) obtained above is most general and is applicable to a mixture of not only a system of any number of components, but also to, all formally similar constants like parachor, rheochor, lyoparachor etc. This equation being very widely applicable will save the time labour and energy of the workers not only in the field of parachor but also in the field of rheochor etc.

Use of this equation is definitely superior to earlier method. Consider the eqn. (5)

$$P_s = \frac{P_m - (1-x)P_a}{x}$$

This equation was being obtained so far, through the equations 1, 2 and 3. The formula (Equation 14) is in fact the same result stated after necessary eliminations. It means that the present equation and the earlier method of using a series of equations 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 are theoretically identical. However when the question of obtaining the numerical values of P_s arises, the various constants involved are bound to be approximate, being accompanied with the errors of estimation and rounding off etc. In such a situation it is quite in order that all the theoretical eliminations are done before the approximate values are substituted and substitution of approximate values prior to eliminations is totally unjustified.

A single example will show the superiority of the use of the method. Since the

2. W. V. Bhagwat *et. al.*, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 249; 1952, 29, 303; 1948, 26, 165; 1948, 25, 275; 1949, 26, 593,

calculated results from the two methods possess a difference of the order of the error. Data for the solution of NH_4Cl in water are as follows:

W_s	WS	W_m	D_m	γ_m	P_s	M_s	MS
11.1898	49.2783	60.4680	1.0520	78.84	52.66	54.602	18.016

Calculations by the classical method using a four figure logarithmic table give the value of $P_s=133.5$ while the value obtained by our equation is $=133.0$. The permissible errors in parachor values generally lie between 0.1–0.9 and hence a difference of 0.5 causes an appreciable error in the result. In some cases the error of the old method may surpass even the permissible error limits.

It can therefore be concluded that the earlier method of using a series of five equations must be replaced by the method suggested by us.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
VIRIAM UNIVERSITY,
USJAIN.

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